

Factors Influencing the Level of Knowledge of Hepatitis B Virus Among Residents of Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The Hepatitis B virus, which is a potentially fatal liver infection, causes hepatitis B (HBV). It is a significant issue for global health since it can lead to chronic infections and a high risk of cirrhosis and liver cancer-related death. The main factor in the spread of HBV is ignorance; there are both acute and chronic forms of HBV. Around two billion people are thought to be infected, and 350 million of those people have the chronic form of the illness. A tropical nation like Nigeria has been found to have a high prevalence of HBV infection, and 75% of its citizens are likely to have come into contact with the virus at some point in their lives. Approximately 18 million Nigerians are currently afflicted. From various regions of the nation, prevalence rates ranging from 4.3% to 23.3% have been observed. Ilorin metropolis is located in one of the states with a high prevalence of HBV, according to existing studies. To determine the factors influencing the level of knowledge of residents of Ilorin metropolis about the hepatitis B virus and to raise awareness of the virus's hidden effects and dangers, the germ theory of diseases and the Health Belief Model (HBM). The survey design, alongside multiple sampling techniques, was used. The questionnaire instrument was administered to 300 respondents, selected using a purposive sampling technique to select three (3) Local Government Areas. To test the hypotheses, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used. The results showed that there are related/correlated responses on the factors influencing the level of knowledge of Hepatitis B virus among residents of Ilorin, Kwara State, and there is a significant relationship between the level of awareness and knowledge of the spread of Hepatitis B in Ilorin metropolis. The hypothesis also reveals that there is a weak relationship between the factors influencing the level of knowledge of Hepatitis "B" among residents of Ilorin. In conclusion, the study clarifies numerous crucial facets of HBV epidemiology in Nigeria. Hepatitis B virus prevalence is high and varies by region. However, a public awareness campaign, mass immunization of children and adults at risk, and the provision of immunostimulatory medication for those who are already infected in Kwara State and throughout Nigeria could reduce the incidence of hepatitis B virus infection.

Keywords: *Cirrhosis, Disease, Knowledge, Metropolis, Chronic, Infection, Life-threatening, Hepatitis B, Awareness.*

Introduction

The Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is a potentially fatal liver infection caused by the hepatitis B virus (HBV). Although various types of diseases have always plagued the human world, it is one of the deadliest to have recently afflicted human societies (WHO, 2015). It can lead to persistent infection and puts people at a high risk of dying from cirrhosis and liver cancer. It is a contagious liver disease that can cause life-threatening complications and ranges

in intensity from a brief illness to a serious condition that lasts a lifetime. The Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2016) notes that it is more contagious and has an infectiousness level 50 to 100 times higher than the Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV/AIDS). Infection with the hepatitis B virus (HBV) is still a significant public health issue in many countries. Hepatitis is a term that refers to liver damage and inflammation of the liver cells (Davis, 2017). One of the several hepatitis viruses, along with hepatitis A, B, C, D, and so on, is hepatitis B. Although each virus type is distinct, hepatitis B and C are the most likely to develop into chronic infections.

Hepatitis B is essentially divided into two types: acute and chronic. Although the illness affects people of various ages and demographics, recent research shows that HBV is most common in young adults and is acquired through injection or sexual contact with drug users. In addition, certain persons are more likely than others to contract the hepatitis B virus (Lokpo et al., 2017). For instance, drug users, those who have body piercings and tattoos, and those who have unprotected sex without being sufficiently educated on sexual negotiation and safe sex practices (ibid, 2014; Olayinka, 2016), people who engage in unprotected intercourse with numerous partners or with an HBV carrier residing with a person who has a persistent HBV infection, a child born to a mother who is ill, have a job where you come in contact with blood. Others include commuters and people who share public amenities carelessly. The virus can stay stable and contagious on surfaces in the environment for at least 7 days. Transmission can take place inadvertently through contact with contaminated surfaces and other objects like toothbrushes, baby bottles, razors, eating utensils, and medical equipment when mucous membranes or open skin breaks are involved. It is a significant concern for world health, yet most people are not aware of it (World Health Organization (WHO), 2016).

The WHO Western Pacific Region and the WHO African Region have high HB prevalence rates, with 6.2% and 6.1% of the adult population affected, respectively, according to the Global Pattern of HBV Epidemic. An estimated 3.3%, 2.0%, and 1.6% of the general population are infected in the WHO Eastern Mediterranean Region, WHO South-East Asia Region, and WHO European Region, respectively. Additionally, 0.7% of people in the WHO Region of the Americas are afflicted. More than 2 billion people worldwide have HBV infection, while 280 million are chronic carriers who keep the virus in their livers. Roughly 2 million of these carriers pass away each year from cirrhosis or primary liver cell cancer brought on by the virus (WHO, 2013). One of the biggest causes of death in Asia and Africa, primary liver cancer, is caused by this virus in 80% of cases (WHO, 2013). Adults with the infection have a chronic carrier rate of 5–10%. The remaining ones successfully rid their bodies of the infection. A quarter of chronic carriers will pass away from liver effects of their ongoing illness; however, some will always be carriers. According to WHO (2013), more than one-third of the world's population already has serologic evidence of HBV infection, 350 million individuals are chronically infected, and about 600,000 deaths from acute or chronic HBV infection are documented each year. Patients who are infected run a greater risk of unknowingly developing serious disease-related issues such as fibrosis, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC).

In several regions of Asia and Africa, the virus has produced a significant epidemic. One of the biggest causes of death in Asia and Africa, primary liver cancer, is caused by this virus in 80% of cases (WHO, 2013). HBV prevalence ranges from 2% in developed nations, where it is uncommon, to roughly 8% in developing countries. Furthermore, it is well known that Hepatitis B is quite prevalent internationally, particularly in Asia and Africa. With an average carrier prevalence of 10–20% among the general population, Sub-Saharan Africa is regarded as a region with significant endemicity. In Sub-Saharan Africa, 70 to 95 percent of adults carry at least one HBV marker. Forty percent of children in West Africa are predicted to be infected by the age of two, and over 90% by the age of ten. These kids have a 20% chronic carrier prevalence. Hyperendemic is defined as a chronic carrier rate in a population of more than 7%. According to a study conducted in Nigeria, 9 to 39% of people have HBV. Over 20 million people are now afflicted in Nigeria, one of the endemic countries (Adoga et al., 2010). It is a significant factor in the development of liver disorders, and persistent HBV infections are frequently fatal conditions linked to cirrhosis, liver cancer, and liver failure (WHO, 2013). Despite being a serious threat to public health, the secret killer hepatitis B has not yet attracted the attention of medical institutions as it should, nor that of legislators and the general public. Even adults lack access to knowledge about the fatal hepatitis B virus, as education about it has been relegated to the background. Due to the marginalization of hepatitis B education, even adults lack access to information about the dangerous disease (Lokpo et al., 2017).

In recent years, researchers have conducted many studies on the problem of HBV, Hepatitis B Virus, a major public health problem worldwide, but it is more prevalent in developing countries (Akor, 2017). More than 2 billion people are infected with HBV worldwide, while some 280 million are chronic carriers, harboring the virus in their liver. About 2 million of these carriers die each year as a result of cirrhosis or primary liver cell cancer induced by the virus (WHO, 2013). This virus is responsible for 80% of all cases of primary liver cancer, which is one of the leading causes of death in Asia and Africa. The secret killer, hepatitis B, has yet to catch the great attention of health institutions, lawmakers, and the general public, even though it is a major threat to public health. Hepatitis B education is often relegated to the background, leaving adults without a reliable source of information about this deadly disease (Amofah, E, 2019).

Aims and Objectives

- i. To determine how well-informed Ilorin Metropolis residents are about the hepatitis B virus.
- ii. To research the hepatitis B virus's agents and causes of transmission among the residents of Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria.
- iii. To assess how HBV affects residents' socioeconomic status.

Literature Review

According to (Rached, Kheir, Saba, & Ammar, 2020) in their study titled, "Knowledge of Hepatitis B among Young Adults in a Higher Learning Institution in Nigeria and Its Implication on Effective Disease Control," Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in all age groups and sexes, and it is a global health problem. Therefore, rather than in North Central Nigeria, this study looks at students' understanding of hepatitis B and their sources of information about it in South West Nigeria (Kwara State). The effectiveness of a country's HBV prevention and control program could be negatively impacted by the fair level of knowledge demonstrated by these young individuals. In health promotion initiatives, particularly those aimed at young adults, adequate health education on the topic of HBV transmission and the understanding that it is preventable needs to be reemphasized. Although this work is very pertinent, it only covers the Southwestern region of the nation; nonetheless, this study attempts to address that gap adequately.

The systematic review and meta-analysis completed in Nigeria between 2000 and 2013 by BM (Musa et al., 2015) is pertinent to the studies carried out in Kano State. Thus, it is necessary to close that deficit in Kwara State. Genotype distribution of the hepatitis B virus in a subset of infected young people in Central Nigeria, by Olumide et al. (2024). The high level of genetic polymorphism of the virus among a subset of infected young individuals in Central Nigeria has led to the identification of ten genotypes (AJ) of the hepatitis B virus (HBV) with unique geographic distribution. The study is also restricted to central Nigeria, which is the area it will examine.

Looking into Olumide et al., (2024) research from December, on the topic of "Risk perception and awareness of hepatitis B infection among cleaners in a tertiary hospital in Nigeria," sheds further light on this. It was also helpful because it was cross-sectional. In a tertiary hospital in Nigeria, cleaning is the main focus. Thus, there is a need to complete the task that is lacking. Knowledge and Awareness of Hepatitis B Virus Infection in Nigeria, by Angela et al. (2019), was also quite helpful to personalize interventions to each cluster. Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Treatment of Hepatitis-B by Natural Medicine Practitioners in South-West Nigeria, by Nimat et al. (2020), showed that health professionals, including practitioners of natural medicine, and the general public may not be aware of the Hepatitis B virus, its mode of transmission, and its means of prevention, which may contribute to an increase in the prevalence of this public health calamity that affects almost 10% of the world's population.

Their research aims to raise practitioners of natural medicine's awareness of the Hepatitis B virus and evaluate their treatment practices in order to determine whether they are contributing to or exacerbating the disease's threat to the general public. Even though their research was restricted to South-West Nigeria, it was highly helpful for our study. However, some gaps have been found in the review of the literature; aside from a few studies that used a mixed method of research, the majority of the reviewed literature used a quantitative method, and those that used a

qualitative method did not provide enough information to draw generalizations about entire populations, particularly because there is a dearth of substantial evidence to support the claim that research has been conducted in Ilorin metropolis about the current investigation.

Information from the literature has revealed some aspects, both positive and negative, which affect Ilorin metropolitan residents' knowledge of and awareness of the hepatitis B virus. In order to identify the elements that may affect knowledge and awareness of the hepatitis B virus, this study examines the underlying factors that affect the level of knowledge of the virus among inhabitants of Ilorin city, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study employs a survey method relying on quantitative data. Consecutive sampling was used to recruit participants for the quantitative component. A standard tool was developed, pilot tested, and used to collect demographic and HBV characteristics. The data were analyzed using IBM SPSS and descriptive and inferential statistics. Purposeful sampling was used to select participants. One (1) district from each of the three Local Government Areas—Tanke (Ilorin South), Zango (Ilorin East), and Taiwo (Ilorin West)—was chosen using purposive sampling. For this study, a sample size of 300 respondents, including 100 citizens from each of the local governments, was used. Questionnaires were used as the study's data collection tool. The formulated hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics, such as Pearson correlation and Chi-Square.

Results

Table 1: Demographic information of the respondents

Demographic Information	Frequency	Percent
Male	264	88.0
Female	36	12.0
Total	300	100.0
	Frequency	Percent
18 – 20	125	41.7
21 - 22	142	47.3
23 - 24	27	9.0
25 and above	6	2.0
Total	300	100.0
	Frequency	Percent

Married	282		94.0
Divorced		6	2.0
Total	288		96.0
Missing system		12	4.0
Total	300		100.0
		Frequency	Percent

Non-formal Education		6	2.0
Primary Education		6	2.0
Secondary Education		39	13.0
Tertiary Education	249		83.0
Total	300		100.0

Table 1 above reveals that the majority of the respondents were males, 264(88%), while 32 (12%) were females. Also, the majority of the respondents were in the age group 18 – 20 and 21 -22, representing 125(41.7%) and 142(47.3%) respectively. 27(9%) were within the age group 23 – 24 and 6(2%) were within the age group 24 – 25yrs. Furthermore, 282 (94%) of them were married, 6 (2%) were divorced, and 12 (4%) of the respondents did not indicate their marital status, which is thus taken as missing values. Finally, majority of the respondent have 249(83%) undergoes tertiary education, 39(13%) secondary education, 6(2%) had non-formal and primary education respectively.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between Socio-economic background and knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis

Table 2: Cross tabulation of gender against knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis

		Have you ever heard of Hepatitis B Virus?				
		Yes	No	Undecided	Total	Person chi-square
What is your gender	Male	57	195	12	264	0.051
	Female	12	18	0	30	

If you answered 'YES' to question 8 above, how did you hear about it?

		If you answered 'YES' to question 8 above, how did you hear about it?						
		Radio/ Television	Inter net	Magazine	People	Others	Total	Person chi-square

What is your gender	Male	50	6	36	0	26	45	6	45	0	202	24	
	Female					12							
Total		56	36	38	51	45	226						0.000

Rate your awareness of Hepatitis B.

		Very High	High	Mode rate	Low	Very Low	Total					
What is your gender	Male	13	6	18	0	64	64	0	85	244	30	
	Female			12		12						
Total		19	18	76	64	97	274					0.000

How well are you informed about the level of Hepatitis B spread?

Hi-

		Very High	High	Moder ate	Low	Very low	Total				
What is your gender	Male	19	0	31	0	63	66	79	6	258	
	Female			12	12					30	
Total		19	31	75	78	85	288				0.002

Hepatitis B is a viral disease that affects The heart?

		Yes	No	Undecided	Total			
What is your gender	Male	122	24	50	0	86	6	258
	Female							30
Total		146	50	92	288			0.002

Through what means is Hepatitis B been Spread?

		Blood	Sexual	Total		
		Sharp Object	Transfusion at Birth	Intercourse	Year	Total
What is your gender	Male	52	89	57	30	228
	Female	6	6	0	12	24
Total		58	95	57	42	252
						0.002

Note: Reject H_0 if Pearson chi-square value (X^2 value) $\leq \alpha$ value (0.005)

Results from the table above reveal that there is a relationship between gender and knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis. This indicates a relationship between responses from both males and females regarding the knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis.

Table 3: Cross tabulation of age-group against knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis

		Have you ever heard of Hepatitis B Virus?			Total	Pearson chi-square
		Yes	No	Undecided		
What is your age group?	18 – 20	12	101	6	119	0.000
	21 – 22	24	112	6	142	
	23 – 24 25 and above	27	0	0	27	
		6	0	0	6	
Total		69	213	12	294	

		If you answered 'YES' to question 8 above, how did you hear about it?					Total	Person chi-square
		Radio/Television	Internet	Magazine	People	Others		
What is your age group?	18 – 20	13	18	12	25	27	95	0.000
	21 – 22	31	18	19	12	18	98	
	23 – 24 25 and above	12	0	7	8	0	27	
		0	0	0	6	0	6	
Total		56	36	38	51	45	226	

		Rate your awareness of Hepatitis B.					Total	square
		Very High	High	Moderate	Low	Low		
What is your age group?	18 – 20	0	0	39	32	42	113	0.000
	21 – 22	19	12	24	32	49	136	
	23 – 24 25 and above	0	6	13	0	0	19	
		0	0	0	0	6	6	
Total		19	18	76	64	97	274	

How well are you informed about the level of Hepatitis B spread?

		Very High	High	Moderate	Low	Very low	Total	
What is your age group?	18 – 20	7	6	18	46	36	113	0.001
	21 – 22	6	18	43	32	43	142	
	23 – 24	6	7	14	0	0	27	
	25 and above	0	0	0	0	6	6	
Total		19	31	75	78	85	288	

Hepatitis B is a viral disease that affects the heart.

		Yes	No	Undecided	Total	Pearson chi-square
What is your age group?	18 – 20	39	32	48	119	0.000
	21 – 22	74	18	44	136	
	23 – 24	27	0	0	27	
	25 and above	6	0	0	6	
Total		146	50	92	288	

Through what means is Hepatitis B been Spread?

		Sharp Object at Birth.	Blood Transfusion Course L	Sexual Interco	Total	Pearson chi-square
What is your age group?	18 – 20	20	38	25	18	101
	21 – 22	32	36	32	18	118
	23 – 24	6	21	0	0	27
	25 and above	0	0	0	6	6
Total		58	95	57	42	252

Note: Reject H₀ if Pearson chi-square value (X² value) ≤ α α-value (0.005)

Results from the table above reveal that there is a relationship between age group and knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis. Meaning that irrespective of the age groups, there are related/correlated responses on the knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis. Thus, we reject H₀.

Hypothesis 2: *There is a relationship between the level of awareness and information among the population and the spread of Hepatitis B in Ilorin metropolis.*

Table 4: *Relationship between how well the people are informed and aware of the level of the spread of Hepatitis B in Ilorin metropolis*

Chi-Square Tests on Knowledge * Awareness

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1030.62	143	.000
	5 ^a		

Note: *Reject H₀ if Pearson chi-square value (X² value) ≤ α α-value (0.005)*

Hepatitis B is prevalent among all
age group?

		Yes	No	d	Total	square
What is your gender?	Male	147	18	87	252	0.000
	Female	12	6	12	30	
Total		159	24	99	282	

Hepatitis B is prevalent among all
age group?

		Yes	No	d	Total	
What is your age group?	18 – 20	53	6	48	107	0.000
	21 – 22	92	12	38	142	
	23 – 24	8	6	13	27	

	25 and above	6	0	0	6
Total		159	24	99	282

Note: Reject H_0 if Pearson chi-square value (X^2 value) \leq a value (0.005)

Results from the table above reveal that there is a relationship between the level of awareness and information among people and the spread of Hepatitis B in Ilorin metropolis. Thus, we reject H_0 .

Hypothesis 3: *There is a relationship between the factors influencing the level of knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis.*

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.480 ^a	.231	.216	.61628

The regression coefficient R (0.480) above shows a weak relationship between the factors influencing the level of knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis. Thus, we do not reject H_0 . We conclude that there is no significant or only a weak relationship between the factors influencing the level of knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis. From the test results obtained, it is revealed that there is a relationship between gender and knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis. This means that there is a relationship between responses from both males and females regarding knowledge of Hepatitis B. Also, there is a relationship between age group and knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis, indicating that irrespective of age, there are correlated responses on the knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents. Furthermore, from the test of the second hypothesis, results reveal that there is a relationship between the level of people's information and their awareness of the spread of Hepatitis B in Ilorin metropolis. Results from the third stated hypothesis reveal that there is a weak relationship between the factors influencing the level of knowledge of Hepatitis B among residents of Ilorin metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

The residents of Ilorin possess limited awareness and understanding of the Hepatitis B Virus (HBV), including its modes of transmission and the serious health risks it poses. Public concern regarding HBV prevention remains low,

and efforts towards awareness and sensitization within the city are insufficient. Despite the relatively high prevalence of HBV in Ilorin, it receives significantly less attention from healthcare professionals compared to diseases such as HIV. This lack of emphasis has left many young individuals particularly vulnerable to the virus. This finding aligns with previous research by Adejoke et al. (2020), who conducted a similar study. Similarly, the work of Olumide et al. (2017) is also relevant to this research. Moreover, the study by Angela et al., (2019), which examined a related area—knowledge of HBV—was instrumental to this study. However, these previous studies had certain gaps, which this research has attempted to address. Such gaps include awareness of HBV through seminars/workshops, media, schools, and Non-Governmental Organizations, among other channels discussed in this research.

Conclusion

This study consequently draws the following conclusions based on its findings and the tested hypotheses: Residents of Ilorin metropolis are largely unaware of HBV, its modes of transmission, and the serious risks it poses. The citizens of Ilorin are largely unconcerned with HBV prevention methods, and awareness and sensitization efforts are quite low. Despite a relatively high prevalence of HBV in the city, medical professionals place less emphasis on it compared to HIV and other diseases, leaving many young people more susceptible to the virus.

Recommendations

In a nutshell, periodic sensitization to the risk of developing the Hepatitis B Virus is necessary. The majority of Nigerians need to be reminded of the looming risks of contracting HBV. The following recommendations were put forth for execution in light of the findings:

- i. It is important to employ both print and electronic media to educate the public.
- ii. To reduce illness transmission, education initiatives should focus on disease awareness.
- iii. The government should raise the socioeconomic standing of the populace to lower the incidence of all viral hepatitis.
- iv. The government should guarantee that everyone has access to information and training on safe and hygienic food handling procedures, and should put in place better sanitation systems.
- v. It is important to ensure that medical waste is disposed of safely in the health sector.

Based on the study's conclusions, both governmental and non-governmental organizations should launch a comprehensive media campaign to raise awareness. Secondly, parents should educate their children about the existence and risks of HBV. The study also recommends that the government organize workshops on HBV for medical professionals and include HBV education in school curricula alongside other infectious diseases. Additionally, the government should allocate funding for immune-stimulatory therapy for individuals already infected, both in Kwara State and across Nigeria, with particular focus on young people and children.

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